

INTENSIVE IMPROVEMENT OF SPEAKING ABILITY THROUGH MODERN METHODS DURING THE STUDY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

Speaking is the most crucial part of language learning cases. For both native and non-natives because, boosting of speech ability requires long time and alternative approach simultaneously. One of the main questions asked by English language learners is about methods of creating atmosphere in English and their importance in speech. According to all instructors, it is a pivotal to create a comfortable zone during the conversation and to speak confidently. Another major problem is that students' ability to round up their ideas and apply alternatives is weakening. This science-based article focuses on ways to solve speech development problems common to all students.

Keywords: speaking, intensive method, vocabulary, linguistic literature

INTRODUCTION

Today, learning and teaching foreign languages is increasing day by day. It's no secret that languages, especially English, are accepted as the language of communication for everyone. Therefore, the performance of students studying it is not low. English has a vital place in medicine, law, social media, sports, and economics. Despite the fact that, it is considered a world language, learning it, talking and communicating in this language is not easy for the most parts of students. A common question that mainly interests instructors is why students fail to construct sentences and express their thoughts even in practical, real-life situations, despite their sufficient knowledge of grammar. The most obvious problem is nervousness and anxiety while speaking because most of them worry about making mistakes and confusing while

speaking. Due to this seemingly simple situation, students' ability to speak in the second language is developing very slowly. This sustained expansion in speaking assessment research calls for a systematic evaluation of key results that may guide future scholars and practitioners through the sea of published work or offer them strong advice for ongoing speaking assessment research. There are now a number of review or position papers on speaking assessment accessible, either examining the advancements in speech assessment more generally. This sustained expansion in speaking assessment research calls for a systematic evaluation of key results that may guide future scholars and practitioners through the sea of published work or offer them strong advice for ongoing speaking assessment research. There are now a number of review or position papers on speaking assessment accessible, either examining the advancements in speech assessment more generally.

METHOD

To begin with, In the process of language learning, each person approaches based on his level of knowledge and interest. As I mentioned above, before using alternative methods of language learning, each student needs to fully analyze his level, because each student accelerates his learning potential and achieves results using a methodology that is suitable for him and in every way. Today, more than 66 percent of the world approves of language learning, with English language learners making up the majority of them. And therefore, there are 1000s of ways and means to save language learners` time. But each student should develop a new way of learning new things based on his potential. For example, listening is one of the most basic and important parts of language learning, however, not all students can get effective results from the full use of this method instead, it may be beneficial for them to read or write while reading. Even many instructors say that movies or music are useful methods for foreign language learners.

RESULT

To begin with, a smartphone is indeed an excellent tool for language training. Use it to record your voice and afterwards play it back to hear how other people perceive your English. Utilize all of your favorite productivity tools to schedule your practice sessions and keep a list of all the new phrases you discover. To understand how words are spoken, listen to English news reports and music. This is another technique to pick up new words and phrases. You learn more the more you pay attention! To improve your pronunciation and discover which words are stressed in a phrase, try mimicking what you hear. Moreover, Read a magazine or a newspaper aloud to yourself. You may

even get the screenplay for your preferred TV program and perform it! This is a terrific technique to practice pronunciation since you don't need to worry about sentence structure or grammar; instead, you just need to make sure your English sounds amazing.

DISSCUSSION

IN THIS PART I AM GOING TO ANALIZE ALL ESSENTIONAL PARTS OF INCREASING SPEAKING ABILITY INTENSIVELE:

- ✚ LEARN A NEW WORD EVERY DAY,
- ✚ WATCHING FILMS AND SERIES ON A DALIY BASIS,
- ✚ MAKE FRIENDS FOR CREATING ENGLISH ATMOSPHERE,
- ✚ DO INTERESTING ACTIVETY IN ENGLISH,
- ✚ HAVE A DEBATE,
- ✚ USE A DICTIONARY EFFECTIVELY.
- ✚ THINK IN ENGLISH.

In all parts of these have more and more crucial futures. First and foremost, for all language learners, **searching** and **building up** vocabulary is the best way of enhancing speaking ability immediately. Next one is called **experimental** and **practical**. Although spending time for watching tv or listening today`s famous English songs seems so an unbelievable way of learning, it can play incredibly significant role in that case. Furthermore, whenever and whatever every language learner has to pay attention to make a **comfortable English zoon**. It can lead to produce productivity. Even students attempt to switch on their phone in English.

DEBEAT- the most powerful ways of fulfilling new knowledge and also Debate all of your personal favorites in English with your peers. Use as much words as you can to make your case, and pay special attention to the opposing points so that you are able convincingly rebut them. There are several excellent dictionary applications for smartphones that you can use to carry a dictionary with you wherever you go. Online dictionaries frequently contain audio samples so you can verify your pronunciation. But be careful not to get overly dependent on them. Try pronouncing the words first, then check to see if you got them properly. Translation in your thoughts is a significant issue during discussions and other circumstances where you need to be able to assimilate information rapidly and reply right away. You become less active. You pause as a result. Sometimes you'll entirely miss the chat since your opportunity to join has passed and you're still translating. In addition, it might be challenging to translate

a lot of slang, idioms, and phrasal verbs fast, if at all. The best thing you can do for your fluency is to quit mentally translating and start thinking in English.

CONCLUSION

You'll feel more secure and prepared to reply when you anticipate the discussion based on experience. To feel more prepared, envision the discussions you want to have in the future and prepare for them beforehand. Prepare yourself for change since things might not go exactly as you planned. You may record the talk and run it through several times. Everyone faces problems and challenges but they can handle all of them in learning process simultaneously.

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